

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN THE REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the formation of the investment climate in the development of the economy of the regions, the negative and positive factors affecting it are presented and analyzed. In addition to the regional economy to increase the inflow of foreign investment what to pay attention is mentioned.

Introduction. The study of investment problems has always attracted the attention of experts, analysts and researchers in the field of economics. The world capital market is facing fierce competition in attracting investments, ensuring that they are attracted in sufficient quantity and quality is one of the priorities of any state.

Creating a favorable investment climate is one of the most important conditions for attracting investment and ensuring sustainable growth of the country's economy.

The textbook, edited by "G. Podshivalenko and N. Kiseleva, states that "one of the most common criteria for making investment

decisions is to assess the investment climate at the macro level and the investment attractiveness of the investment object."

"As we study the research of Uzbek and many other foreign scholars on 'investment climate' and 'investment attractiveness', we find that there is no single definition of these categories in their research. Some authors use these two terms as synonyms. The investment climate is a very complex and multifaceted concept.

Methods and materials. As well as, The application of high quality to "investment costs" is also encouraged. In particular, B.A.Okhunov helped to ensure an optimal investment system: "Optimal investment is

a state strategy for the implementation of investment activities and political, socio-economic and economic-legal standards formed by discussing the risks and interests of investors”.

Ensuring sustainable economic growth depends primarily on pursuing a prudent investment policy in the country. One of the goals that can be seen from running a public investment company is to constantly help create a favorable investment for foreign investors. Today, Uzbekistan has such a favorable environment for investors. These include a system to protect and encourage investors.

In the economic literature we come across economic categories such as "investment climate", "investment environment", "investable climate". In our opinion, since each of these concepts has the same meaning, that is, it is a synonym, we use the concept of "investment environment" based on the rules of the Uzbek language.

In our opinion, "Investment environment" means a set of economic, social, political, legal factors and conditions aimed at ensuring the efficiency and security of investments in the country's economy. The state of the investment climate requires a created legal framework and its foundations, a quality structure of legislation and their compliance.

The existence of a stable political and economic environment in the country, the creation of a favorable investment climate and the effectiveness of the system of foreign capital is a prerequisite for attracting foreign investment. The investment climate is a general criterion for the placement of investment resources, primarily ensuring the return on capital investment.

In the process of assessing the investment climate, the investor determines the level of investment risk. If the worse the investment return, the higher the investor sets its quarterly risk.

At the same time, we describe the following constituent elements of the investment climate, which reflect the conditions of investment activities. Its main components are the concepts of investment activity, investment potential and investment attractiveness, which take the level of investment risk. It is necessary to moderate investment in attracting foreign capital to our country and increase the investment attractiveness of the regions. In general, the concepts of investment environment and attractiveness are different concepts related to investment.

Results and discussion. Investment attractiveness is a system of organizational and economic activities associated with the principle of "ringing" in order to inform investors about the existing potential of the investment climate after its formation. Among the factors that have a positive impact on the inflow of foreign investment into the economy of Uzbekistan, we can include the following:

- ☒ availability of cheap and skilled labor;
- ☒ the republic is rich in natural and economic resources;
- ☒ the natural and climatic conditions of the country have the potential to produce large quantities of agricultural raw materials;
- ☒ the prospects of the national market;
- ☒ political and economic stability in the country;
- ☒ formation of a favorable regulatory framework.

Factors affecting the investment environment can be grouped into positive and negative factors according to the outcome of the impact

Positive factors are a set of factors that affect the improvement of the investment climate, which can include the economic situation, socio-economic stability, the level of development of entrepreneurship, its laws and regulations, culture and spirituality, the interest of investors.

Negative factors are a set of factors that adversely affect the improvement of the investment climate, including economic and political instability, poor tax system, underdeveloped infrastructure, shortcomings in the insurance mechanism, lack of accurate information for investment projects, underdeveloped securities market, etc. (1-photo).

1-photo. Factors affecting the investment climate¹.

The economic literature emphasizes that the creation of an investment climate depends on the influence of many factors², its analysis focuses on internal and external characteristics and the level of development of the investment climate in

this area, its attractiveness and the importance of methods of determining investment risk are recognized³.

Improving the investment climate depends primarily on increasing the level of investment attractiveness.

¹Compiled by the author.

²Brodsky M.N., Kostenko S.I. Investments as a source of competitiveness // Uchenye zapiski Institute of Law of St. Petersburg State University of Economics and Finance. / Ed. A.A.Livrevsky. - St. Petersburg, 2001. Issue. 6. P.95.

³<http://ifc.org>, <http://economic-dictionary.ru>

Investment attractiveness is the assessment of the investment of a country, industry or any individual enterprise in terms of profitability, development prospects and level of investment risk. Investment attractiveness is determined by the simultaneous influence of the factors that shape the level of investment potential and investment risk. By assessing such indicators, it is possible to determine the expediency, attractiveness and level of investment risk of investments. The level of investment risk is directly related to the investment environment.

At the macroeconomic level, the investment climate is reflected in the bilateral relations between investors and government agencies, businesses. The investable environment is an objective situation for any specific period of time and includes a set of conditions available for investing. The investment climate is formed under the influence of government management and is one of the important factors of public investment policy. In this sense, each state will have its own system of receiving capital when investing. The system of capital acceptance is a set of state policies and laws, normative documents on foreign capital. Encouraging investment in the economy of Uzbekistan is constantly improving. In relation to foreign investment, laws and decisions are being developed on the basis of modern rules of international economic relations, and foreign investment infrastructure is being created.

All the above factors are important for foreign investors, and there are firms and

organizations in developed countries that evaluate special investment projects, study the investment climate in countries interested in attracting investment and provide conclusions for investors. In particular, the authoritative information services of a number of countries, such as Switzerland and Germany, use the BERI (business environment risk index) index to assess the economic, political and social situation of the country on the basis of 15 important indicators, each of which is assessed on a scale of 0 unsatisfactory and very favorable. "BERI" the index is published 3 times a year by countries of the world.

An investment environment is a concept that is used in a very broad sense and covers all the issues and issues that are taken into account by the investor. The investor evaluates the pros and cons of investing in a particular country, while paying close attention to the ideology, politics, economy, and culture of the country in which it seeks to invest its capital.

A comprehensive, in-depth analysis of the investment climate underlies investment risk. The investment climate and risk levels are inversely related. That is, the more favorable the investment environment, the lower the risk of the investor's entrepreneurial capital, and this will increase the inflow of investors. Conversely, the more unfavorable the investment environment, the higher the risk level. This leads to an increase in the costs to the recipient of the investment⁴.

The issue of creating a positive investment climate should be interpreted as a key

⁴Pinali E. Investment climate and private sector. // Ekonomicheskoe obozrenie. 2005. № 9, pp.42-43.

process in the globalization of the economy and the consequent expansion of access to investment resources, which in turn should not be overlooked as economic competition between investors increases. If we want to increase the volume of foreign investment, of course, we must make the investment climate, regional conditions more acceptable and higher than competitors, to

ensure a favorable and "risk-free" climate to stimulate national investment. Otherwise, there will be a sharp decline in investment in the country and the outflow of funds from local investors. The investor is required to have a complete picture of the attractiveness of the investment climate when deciding to invest in its own territory or in other regions. (2-photo).

2-photo. Description of the levels of attractiveness of the investment environment⁵

Conclusion.

As a result of our research, we include the following in the structure of the investment climate:

- investment potential is the openness of the country to the inflow of investments and the availability of reserves of economic resources, determined by their size.
- investment risk is the probability that investors will make or lose a profit based on the conditions created for them.

Investment potential can be divided into the following groups: natural resource

potential; production capacity; innovative potential; labor potential; financial capacity; institutional capacity; infrastructure capacity ; consumption capacity ; tourist capacity. The attractiveness of a country for investors is determined primarily by the investment climate. Attractiveness is assessed at the macro and micro levels. At the macro level, attractiveness encompasses social, political, economic, and other aspects of a host country's life⁶.

⁵Compiled by the author

⁶Turobov, S., Muzaffarova, K., Alimxanova, N., & Azamatova, G. (2020). INCREASING THE

Any potential investor, first of all, takes into account the general state of the economy of the territory of the country and its individual sectors. One of the important aspects to consider is labor costs.

At the micro level, the new environment is reflected in the agreements of investors, the relationship of firms with public administration and business entities. Therefore, in order to increase the inflow of foreign investment into the region's economy, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- first, the formation of an investment climate in the regions;
- second, increase the scale of factors that have a positive impact on the formation of the investment climate;
- third, increase the investment attractiveness of the regions;
- fourth, increase the investment potential of business entities in the regions;
- fifth, minimizing the level of investment risk of entrepreneurs, etc.

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